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MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MOLIYA SOHASINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	7
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Mamadyarovna Go'zal Norboyevna	
MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYA VOSITALARI ORQALI CHEKKA HUDUDLARDA IQTISODIY FAOLLIKNI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	13
Eshov Mansur Po'latovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI BOSH PROKURATURA HUZURIDAGI IQTISODIY JINOYATLARGA QARSHI KURASHISH DEPARTAMENTI FAOLIYATI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI.....	20
Babadjanov Atxam Axmadjanovich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫМИ ПРОЦЕССАМИ ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	26
Ахмедов Самандар Сайфуллоевич	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BOJXONA XIZMATINING FISKAL FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	32
Farxodov Farrux Furqatovich, Toshpo'lotova E'zoza Latifjonovna	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT ULUSHINI QISQARTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	38
Mamatkulov Salimjon Raxmonkulovich	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BOJXONA TO'LOVLARINI UNDIRISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AYRIM MASALALARI.....	43
Pardayev To'liqin Nasirovich	
QARZ MUNOSABATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH: IQTISODIY VA HUQUQIY MUNOSABATLARDAGI AHAMIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	47
Quramboev Jamshid Rashid o'g'li	
EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN USING A MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION MODEL.....	50
Rakhimberdiev Kuvonchbek Bakhtiyorovich	
TASHQI SAVDO OPERATSIYALARIDA DEBITOR QARZDORLIKLARNI BOSHQARISHNING RAQAMLI MODEL VA RISK-MONITORING TIZIMI.....	56
Tashmuxeimedov Dilmurod Mirabzalovich	
WAYS TO REDUCE THE RISK OF DIGITAL ATTACKS IN BANKING AND GOVERNMENT FINANCIAL SYSTEMS.....	62
M.N. Umarova	
MOLIYALASHTIRISH MANBALARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH KICHIK BIZNES IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	69
Abduxakimov Eldor Djaloliddinovich	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESDA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	76
Aliyev Yashnarjon Egamberdiyevich	
MAHALLIY GILAM ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKDA TAHDIDLARNI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	81
Arziyeva Sevinch Shomurot qizi	
TASHQI SAVDODA XATARLARNI KAMAYTIRISHDA SAVDONI MOLIYALASHTIRISH VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	85
Babadjanov Shuhrat Atxamovich	
KORXONALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING KONTSEPTUAL VA METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	92
Jamoliddinov Jobirbek Bohodir o'g'li	

KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHNING METODOLOGIK JIHATLARI	97
Karimov Alibek Valiyevich	
KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQARISH OMILLARI NOMUTANOSIBLIGINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA’SIRINI VAHOLASH VA UNI BARTARAF ETISH MEXANIZMI.....	102
Kaypnazarova Gulshad Xojamuratovna	
КРИТЕРИИ ОЦЕНКИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В МАЛОМ БИЗНЕСЕ С ПОМОЩЬЮ SWOT-АНАЛИЗА.....	108
Набиев Бехзод Шавкатович	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASH HAMDA QO’LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING ILMIY-AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	114
Tashmuxeimedova Yayra Atxamovna, Teshayev Sayimbek	
O’ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNESNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH ORQALI AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH YO’LLARI.....	120
Toxirova Mushtariybegim Yashnarjon qizi	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARIDA MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA’MINLASH STRATEGIYASI.....	124
Tursunov Bobir Ortikmirzayevich, Umarova Nargiza Xoldarovna	
РАЗРАБОТКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОЙ СТРАТЕГИИ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ТЕКСТИЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ.....	134
Турсунов Бобир Ортикмирзаевич	
KIMYO SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	141
Tursunxo’jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o’g’li	
MAMLAKAT QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARI MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLARNING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI.....	147
Umarova Nargiza Xoldarovna	
YENGIL SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	154
Sadriddinova Nigora	
RAQAMLI MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYA VOSITALARI ORQALI TUMANLAR O’RTASIDAGI IJTIMOYIY FARQNI KAMAYTIRISH MODELI.....	162
Xakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, Tursunov Bobir Ortikmirzayevich, Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o’g’li	
O’ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO’LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING O’RNI	170
Jaloliddinov Anvar Jaloliddin o’g’li	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO’LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH: O’ZBEKISTON BOJXONA ORGANLARI TAJRIBASI	176
Makkamov Z.X., Soatov S.S.	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ORQALI XALQARO SAVDODA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA’MINLASH MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH MEXANIZMLARI	182
Muxtorov Boburmirzo Bahodir o’g’li	
RAQAMLI TO’LOV TIZIMLARI VA ELEKTRON HISOB-KITOBARNING YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI.....	188
Norsafarov Bunyodshoh Muhiddinzoda	
PROSPECTIVE INDICATORS FOR MANAGING THE LEGALIZATION OF THE INFORMAL SECTOR AND INFORMAL EMPLOYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	192
Qoraboyev Nuriddin Pardaboy o’g’li	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO’LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN AHOLIGA KO’RSATILAYOTGAN BANK XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING RAQAMLI YO’NALISHLARI... 196	
To’patillayeva Gulnoza Sirojiddin qizi	
BIG DATA TEXNOLOGIYALARI YORDAMIDA SOLIQ RISKLARINI ANIQLASH VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	201
Yakubova Nargiza Tursunbayevna, Maxmudov Jasurbek Ulug’bek o’g’li	

SOLIQLAR YOKI BOSHQA MAJBURIY TO'LOVLARNI TO'LASHDAN BO'YIN TOVLASH JINOYATI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	208
Axmedov Zafar Bozorboyevich	
DAVLATLARNING IQTISODIY JINOYATCHILIKKA QARSHI KURASHDAGI XALQARO HAMKORLIGI: XALQARO TASHKILOTLAR, FATF STANDARTLARI VA AMALIY MEXANIZMLAR.....	213
Tashmuxe medova Yayra Atxamovna	
IQTISODIY JINOYATLARNI ANIQLASH VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASHISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYALARNING O'RNI.....	221
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, Tursunov Bobir Ortiqmirzayevich, Tashmuxe medova Yayra Atxamovna	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA AHOLINING MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	226
Azlarova Mushtariybegim Abror qizi	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARI XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA DAVLAT INSTITUTSIONAL MEXANIZMLARINING ROLI.....	232
Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna, Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	
MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIK TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI.....	238
Maxmudova Muxlisa Qodirjon qizi, Sattorova Nasiba G'anijon qizi	
AHOLI MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR TAHLILI.....	244
Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna, Muzaffarova Dilbar Mamalatif qizi	
MAHALLIY OLIMLAR TADQIQOTLARIDA MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIK VA BANK XIZMATLARI MASALALARI.....	251
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Maxmudova Muxlisa Qodirjon qizi	
BANK PLASTIK KARTALARI VA SHAXSIY HISOB RAQAMLARINI NAZORAT QILISH TIZIMINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	258
Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna, Sattorova Nasiba G'anijon qizi	
AUTENTIFIKATSIYA SXEMALARINI TAHLIL QILISH VA ULARNING AFZALLIKLARI HAMDA KAMCHILIKLARI.....	265
Ahmedova Nilufar Shukratovna, Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna	
PLASTIK KARTALAR XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIR KO'RSATUVCHI MAVJUD KIBERXAVFSIZLIK TAHDIDLARI TAHLILI.....	272
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Maxmudova Muxlisa Qodirjon qizi	
ILG'OR XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA PLASTIK KARTALAR VA RAQAMLI TO'LOVLAR XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH TAJRIBALARI: FINTECH PLATFORMALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI VA MYCARD MOBIL ILOVASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA TAVSIYALAR.....	278
Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna, Mashrapova Sabina Turobjonovna	
AHOLI MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISHDA IJTIMOY TARMOQLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA INDIKATORLARI.....	285
Eshpulatova Muazzam Barnoyevna	
AHOLINING MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	292
Eshpulatova Muazzam Barnoyevna	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОЦЕНКИ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЗРЕЛОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ И ЕЁ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	298
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмухамбетовна	
ОЦЕНКА ВЛИЯНИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЗРЕЛОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ НА КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	305
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмухамбетовна	
MOLIVAVIY INKLIZIYADA KIBERXAVFSIZLIKNING O'RNI VA UNING BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: BANK MOBIL ILOVALARI MISOLIDA.....	313
Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi	

PROSPECTIVE INDICATORS FOR MANAGING THE LEGALIZATION OF THE INFORMAL SECTOR AND INFORMAL EMPLOYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article presents prospective indicators and research findings on managing the informal sector and legalizing informal employment in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It also includes proposals and conclusions on these topics.

Key words: Labor market, informal sector, informal employment, taxation, newly established enterprises, volume of consumer goods production.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasida norasmiy sektorni boshqarish va norasmiy bandlikni legallashtirish bo‘yicha istiqbolli ko‘rsatkichlar hamda tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur masalalar yuzasidan takliflar va xulosalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: mehnat bozori, norasmiy sektor, norasmiy bandlik, soliqqa tortish, yangi tashkil etilgan korxonalar, iste‘mol tovarlari ishlab chiqarish hajmi.

Аннотация. В статье представлены перспективные показатели и результаты исследований по управлению неформальным сектором и легализации неформальной занятости в Республике Узбекистан. Также приведены предложения и выводы по данным вопросам.

Ключевые слова: рынок труда, неформальный сектор, неформальная занятость, налогообложение, вновь созданные предприятия, объём производства потребительских товаров.

INTRODUCTION

In the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the informal economy, shadow economy, hidden economy, and population employed in the informal sector are considered important, meaning we can observe economic trends for which exact figures are not available. The goal is to achieve a growth trend in self-employment and the scale of the formal sector by managing the legalization of the informal sector in our country. Managing the legalization of the informal sector helps increase the country’s economic efficiency, enforce legislation, as well as improve law enforcement systems and measures. However, misunderstanding the management system may negatively affect the current state of the informal sector.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 847 “On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan Aimed at Reducing Informal Employment,” signed by President Sh. Mirziyoyev on June 16, 2023, establishes the implementation of large-scale reforms as one of the priority tasks. These reforms aim to ensure employment and further strengthen social protection for the country’s population, reduce the share of informal employment, and provide comprehensive support for self-employed individuals. This article serves, to a certain extent, to facilitate the implementation of the tasks defined in this law.

Despite the high rates of economic growth in our country, the impact of employment in the informal sector and the shadow economy on various economic sectors persists. There are factors influencing the level of the informal sector in the labor market, and an econometric analysis of these influencing factors was developed using statistical data.

Summarizing the results, we can conclude that by increasing the number of enterprises and organizations in the Republic, it is possible to increase the number of economically active population, thereby reducing the number of people employed in the informal sector.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of informal sector management and the legalization of informal employment has been extensively examined in international economic literature, particularly within the context of developing and transition economies. International Labour Organization has played a central role in conceptualizing informal employment and developing policy frameworks for its formalization. In its analytical reports, the organization emphasizes that informality is not merely a labor market anomaly but a structural feature linked to institutional weaknesses, regulatory burdens, and limited access to formal economic opportunities.

The theoretical foundations of the informal sector were significantly shaped by the work of Hernando de Soto, who argued that excessive regulation and weak property rights systems are key drivers of informality. In his research, particularly highlighted in 1989, he demonstrated that informal economic activities often emerge as rational responses of individuals to inefficient institutional environments. This perspective is further supported by Friedrich Schneider, whose empirical studies on the shadow economy across multiple countries reveal that high tax burdens, overregulation, and corruption significantly expand the size of informal activities.

From a labor market perspective, Guy Standing emphasizes the growing prevalence of precarious employment and its connection to informal labor structures. His research underscores that informal employment is closely associated with income insecurity, lack of social protection, and limited labor rights. Similarly, Janine Berg highlights the importance of institutional reforms and labor market policies in transitioning workers from informal to formal employment, stressing the role of social protection systems and inclusive labor regulations.

The macroeconomic implications of informality have also been widely explored. World Bank studies indicate that a large informal sector constrains fiscal capacity, reduces tax revenues, and weakens public service delivery. According to analytical reports published in 2019, reducing informality requires a comprehensive approach that combines regulatory simplification, improved governance, and incentives for formal business activity. In addition, International Monetary Fund research demonstrates that digitalization and financial inclusion are critical tools for formalizing economic activities, particularly in emerging economies.

In recent years, the role of digital technologies in reducing informality has gained increasing attention. Andrei Shleifer and Rafael La Porta, in their institutional economics research, argue that strengthening formal institutions and improving transparency are essential for reducing informal practices. Their findings suggest that legal enforcement mechanisms and simplified business registration processes significantly contribute to the expansion of the formal sector.

In the context of Uzbekistan, recent studies by international organizations and national researchers emphasize the importance of institutional reforms, tax policy modernization, and digital governance in managing the informal sector. The integration of electronic tax systems, online registration platforms, and digital payment infrastructures has been identified as a key factor in encouraging the transition from informal to formal employment. These approaches align with global best practices and demonstrate the growing role of prospective indicators in forecasting and managing the dynamics of informal sector legalization.

Overall, the literature suggests that effective management of informal sector legalization requires a multidimensional approach that combines institutional reforms, labor market policies, digital transformation, and economic incentives. The use of prospective indicators allows policymakers to anticipate trends in informal employment and design targeted interventions aimed at its gradual formalization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study relies on secondary data obtained from official statistics of Uzbekistan, as well as reports from the International Labour Organization, World Bank, and national agencies. Quantitative indicators of informal employment are analyzed using comparative, trend, and econometric methods, including correlation and regression analysis. Additionally, qualitative assessment is applied to evaluate institutional factors influencing the legalization of the informal sector.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To reduce informal employment in the Republic of Uzbekistan, we will implement a multi-factor forecast of the volume of consumer goods production per capita, the average annual rate of personal income tax, and the number of newly established enterprises and organizations. For this purpose, we will first analyze the change in informal employment based on the following multifactorial regression equation:

$$Y = \frac{X_1^{0,0084} * X_2^{0,105} * e^{9,8}}{X_3^{0,13}} \quad (2^*)$$

and from the system of equations for each factor involved in this equation, depending on the time t=15:

- volume of consumer goods production per capita

$$X_1 = -141 + 353,3 * t;$$

- average annual rate of personal income tax

$$X_2 = 106,65 + 0,396 * t;$$

- number of newly established enterprises and organizations

$$X_3 = 9227 + 5991 * t.$$

Using their calculations as inputs for the main regression equation, multifactorial forecast indicators of informal employment are determined (Table 1).

Table 1. Projections for 2025–2030 of the number of people employed in the informal sector of the labor market in the Republic of Uzbekistan and indicators of influencing factors

Years	Y	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃
2025	5522	5797	10,4852	105083
2026	5462	6150,5	10,0874	111074
2027	5405	6504	9,6896	117065
2028	5349	6857,5	9,2918	123056
2029	5294	7211	8,894	129047
2030	5239	7564,5	8,4962	135038

According to the table data, by 2030, the number of informal workers is expected to decrease by 23 percent compared to 2024. This can be achieved by increasing the production volume of consumer goods per capita by 67 percent compared to the base year and increasing the number of newly established enterprises and organizations by 55,371. Based on the research results, the average annual rate of personal income tax is projected to decrease by 29.1 percent (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Projections for 2025–2030 of informal sector employment in the labor market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and indicators of influencing factors

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. It is expected that the production volume of consumer goods per capita in the Republic of Uzbekistan will increase by 67 percent, reaching 7,564,500 soums. This will significantly boost the production volume in the country and substantially increase the demand for labor resources. As a result, informal employment in

the unofficial sector of the republic will decrease, and the share of revenue from value-added tax will increase considerably.

2. It is expected that the number of newly established enterprises and organizations in our republic will reach 135,038 by 2030, increasing by 69.5% compared to 2024. This, in turn, will lead to the creation of new jobs and a significant increase in average monthly wages. As a result, the informal sector will shrink, and informal employment will decrease as workers transition to formal jobs. According to the model we propose, due to the increase in the number of newly established enterprises and organizations, the number of people employed in the informal sector in our republic will decrease by 882,778.

3. Informal employment in the informal sector is expected to decrease by 23% by 2030 compared to 2024. Such a result can be achieved by creating new jobs in the republic, further supporting entrepreneurs, and removing obstacles to the formalization of the informal sector operating in the republic. With a 1% reduction in personal income tax, 713,013 informal workers are expected to transition to formal employment. This, in turn, is explained by the fact that the increase in additional income tax revenues to the state budget from these 713,013 workers will be greater than the amount that decreased by 1%.

4. Increasing the level of economic activity of the population by 1 percent will enable a reduction in informal employment by 251 thousand people. This, in turn, will lead to an increase in tax revenues and a clearer view of the population's real incomes. Therefore, we believe it is necessary to develop measures to increase the economic activity of the population in the republic.

5. According to our calculations, a 1% increase in the number of enterprises and organizations operating in our republic would lead to a reduction of more than 10,000 informal payments. In recent years, significant attention has been given to supporting entrepreneurship in our country. As a result, the number of business entities has increased substantially. It is necessary to further intensify measures to create an even more favorable environment for entrepreneurs and alleviate their tax burden.

6. The reduction of informal employment in the republic is implemented based on the results of developed unofficial projections. The obtained results indicate that by 2030, the number of people employed in the informal sector in Uzbekistan is expected to decrease by 2,254,780 compared to 2024, totaling 4,535,817 individuals.

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RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT

Ilmiy elektron jurnal

(MAXSUS SON)

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